

THE KINETICS OF THE FERRIC THIOSULPHATE REACTION. PART I

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From the mechanism involving the two intermediates FeS_2O_3^+ and $\text{Fe}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2^-$, suggested for the ferric thiosulphate reaction (Patnaik and Mahapatra, *Curr. Sci.*, 1955, 24, 195), kinetic equations have been derived for the initial and maximum rates of decay which have been measured spectrophotometrically at different ionic strengths for varying concentrations of ferric and thiosulphate ions. The initial rate varies as the first power of the concentrations of the ferric ion and the square of the concentration of the thiosulphate ion. On the other hand, the maximum rate varies as the square of the concentration of the coloured complex FeS_2O_3^+ . These observations conform to the kinetic equations derived for the rates from the proposed mechanism, the various steps of which consist of bimolecular reactions between oppositely charged ions and ion-pairs. The decrease in rates, both initial and maximum, with the increase in ionic strength substantiates the fact that the rate-controlling stages are reactions involving oppositely charged ions.

The over-all ferric thiosulphate reaction is represented by

A labile coloured complex is formed when a solution of thiosulphate is added to that of a ferric salt. This coloured complex has been shown to possess the formula FeS_2O_3^+ (Das, Nanda and Patnaik, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 459). The decay curve of this complex FeS_2O_3^+ is of S-shape, which suggests the autocatalytic nature of the decay. In order to explain this autocatalytic nature, the following mechanism was suggested (Patnaik and Mahapatra, *Curr. Sci.*, 1955, 24, 195).

The mechanism put forward above can be written in the following set of equations:

where $\text{A} = \text{Fe}^{3+}$; $\text{B} = \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$; $\text{AB} = \text{FeS}_2\text{O}_3^+$; $\text{AB}_2 = \text{Fe}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2^-$, products = $2\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{S}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$ and k_1, k_2 , etc. are velocity constants of the various reactions.

$$\text{So } \frac{-d(\text{AB})}{dt} = k_1(\text{A})(\text{B}) + k_2(\text{AB})(\text{B}) + k_3(\text{AB}_2)(\text{AB}) + k_4(\text{AB}_2) + k_6(\text{AB})$$

Reactions (i) and (vi) have been shown by Schmid (*Z. physikal Chem.*, 1930, 148, 321) to be extremely rapid and therefore $k_1(A)(B) = k_2(AB)$ is maintained throughout. And so

$$-\frac{d(AB)}{dt} = k_2(AB)(B) + k_3(AB_2)(AB) - k_4(AB_2) \quad \dots (2)$$

When the rate attains a maximum value at the quasi-stationary state, the rate of formation of the intermediate AB_2 must be equal to its rate of disappearance. Hence,

$$k_2(AB)(B) = k_3(AB_2)(AB) + k_4(AB_2)(A) + k_5(AB_2)$$

$$\text{Hence,} \quad (AB_2) = \frac{k_2(AB)(B)}{k_3(AB) + k_4(A) + k_5}$$

Substituting this value of (AB_2) in equation (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{d(AB)}{dt} (\text{max}) &= k_2(AB)^2 \left[\frac{2k_2(B) + k_4 \frac{(A)(B)}{(AB)}}{k_3(AB) + k_4(A) + k_5} \right] \\ &= k_2(AB)^2 \left[\frac{2k_2(B) + k_4 \frac{k_6}{k_1}}{k_3(AB) + k_4(A) + k_5} \right] \\ &= \frac{k_2 k_4 k_6}{k_1} (AB)^2 \left[\frac{\frac{2k_1 k_2 (B)}{k_4 k_6} + 1}{k_3(AB) + k_4(A) + k_5} \right] \quad \dots (3) \end{aligned}$$

In equations (iii) and (iv), AB_2 is involved and, further, (AB) is dependent on (A) . It would therefore be quite in order to substitute $k_3(AB) + k_4(A)$ by $k'_3(AB)$, the physical implication being that the rate represented by (iv) bears a constant relationship with that represented by (iii). So equation (3) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{d(AB)}{dt} (\text{max}) &= \frac{k_2 k_4 k_6}{k_1} (AB)^2 \left[\frac{\frac{2k_1 k_2 (B)}{k_4 k_6} + 1}{k'_3(AB) + k_5} \right] \\ &= \frac{k_2 k_4 k_6}{k_1 k_5} (AB)^2 \left[\frac{\frac{2k_1 k_2}{k_4 k_6} + 1}{\frac{k'_3(AB)}{k_5} + 1} \right] = k (AB)^2 \left[\frac{1 + m(B)}{1 + n(AB)} \right] \end{aligned}$$

It can be seen from Table III that the ratio of the initial concentration of B to that of AB varies from 4 to 8. So, if the value of n be on the average 6 times that of m , then

$$\frac{1 + m(B)}{1 + n(AB)} \approx 1,$$

and hence,

$$-\frac{d(AB)}{dt} (\text{max}) = k(AB)^2.$$

In other words

$$(AB)^2 / -\frac{d(AB)}{dt} (\text{max}) = \text{constant} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

However, in the initial stage, $(AB)_0 = 0$ and so the rate of decay becomes

$$-\frac{d(AB)}{dt} (\text{initial}) = k_2(AB)(B) = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_3}(A)(B)^2 = k'(A)(B)^2.$$

In other words

$$(A)(B)^2 / -\frac{d(AB)}{dt} (\text{initial}) = \text{constant} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental details have been described previously (Das *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). The ionic strength was maintained by addition of sodium perchlorate. The H^+ -ion concentration was maintained constant at 0.05 M and the working temperature was $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. In Tables I and II the actual concentrations of Fe^{3+} (A) and $S_2O_3^{2-}$ (B) have been recorded in moles per litre. The effective concentrations have been shown in Table III. Also in Tables I and II, $\log I$ has been noted against time, $\log I_0$ being always 2 for 100% transmission. The values of $\log I$ recorded against zero-time were obtained by extrapolation of the $\log I$ -time curve.

The rates of decay, both initial and maximum, have been calculated as follows. Let C_1 and C_2 be the concentrations of $FeS_2O_3^+$ at times t_1 and t_2 respectively.

$$\text{Then the rate} = \frac{C_1 - C_2}{t_2 - t_1} = \frac{\log(I_0/I_{t_1}) - \log(I_0/I_{t_2})}{e. c. d. (t_2 - t_1)}.$$

Since $e. c. d. = \log(I_0/I)$ (Bears law), where ϵ = extinction coefficient and d = thickness of the liquid layer.

The mean concentration of $FeS_2O_3^+$ is represented by

$$\frac{C_1 + C_2}{2} = \frac{\log\left(\frac{I_0}{I_{t_1}}\right) + \log\left(\frac{I_0}{I_{t_2}}\right)}{\epsilon. d.} = \frac{2 - \frac{1}{2}(\log I_{t_1} + \log I_{t_2})}{e. d.}$$

since I_0 is always 2 for 100% incident transmission.

All measurements were made at the wave-length of $5000\text{\AA}$.

TABLE I

 $\mu = 0.12.$

Time.	Log I at compositions				Time.	Log I at compositions			
	(A)=10 (B)=5	(A)=5 (B)=10	(A)=5 (B)=5	(A)=5 (B)=7.5		(A)=10 (B)=5	(A)=5 (B)=10	(A)=5 (B)=5	(A)=5.5 (B)=7.5
0 sec.	1.061	0.966	1.390	1.157	55 sec.	1.851	1.762	1.780	1.778
5	1.079	1.000	1.398	1.176	60	1.892	1.792	1.810	1.808
10	1.114	1.070	1.415	1.211	65	1.924	1.823	1.834	1.834
15	1.176	1.154	1.443	1.273	70	1.948	1.840	1.856	1.853
20	1.255	1.249	1.477	1.342	75	1.964	1.854	1.875	1.869
25	1.357	1.347	1.519	1.419	80	1.973	1.869	1.889	1.884
30	1.455	1.447	1.565	1.505	85	1.982	1.885	1.903	1.896
35	1.562	1.535	1.615	1.574	90	1.986	1.895	1.914	1.906
40	1.648	1.608	1.663	1.639	95	...	1.905	1.920	1.914
45	1.738	1.672	1.708	1.697	100	...	1.911	1.929	1.920
50	1.796	1.720	1.748	1.740					

TABLE II

Time.	Log I at compositions				Time.	Log I at compositions			
	(A)=10 (B)=10	(A)=10 (B)=5	(A)=5 (B)=10	(A)=5 (B)=5		(A)=10 (B)=10	(A)=10 (B)=5	(A)=5 (B)=10	(A)=5 (B)=5
	$\mu = 0.25.$					$\mu = 0.45.$			
0 sec.	0.710	1.320	1.320	1.622	1.050	1.507	1.490	1.735	
10	0.860	1.342	1.357	1.636	1.122	1.516	1.519	1.742	
20	1.138	1.447	1.466	1.665	1.301	1.565	1.586	1.756	
30	1.431	1.588	1.599	1.701	1.498	1.636	1.658	1.775	
40	1.648	1.728	1.708	1.748	1.658	1.718	1.724	1.798	
50	1.775	1.836	1.785	1.789	1.769	1.794	1.782	1.823	
60	1.845	1.906	1.839	1.826	1.836	1.856	1.848	1.848	
70	1.889	1.948	1.875	1.857	1.878	1.903	1.859	1.872	
80	1.918	1.969	1.903	1.885	1.906	1.935	1.855	1.895	
90	1.935	1.979	1.919	1.903	1.910	1.954	1.903	1.913	
100	1.946	1.983	1.932	1.929	1.933	1.967	1.917	1.924	

TABLE III

[The concentrations of A, B and AB have been expressed in m. moles per litre. The initial and maximum rates (I. R and M.R.) have been expressed in m. moles per litre per second].

Initial conc. (A).	Effective initial conc. (B).	Effective initial conc. (A).	Effective initial conc. (B).	I.R. $\times 10^3$.	$\frac{(A)(B)^2}{I.R.} \times 10^{-4}$.	M.R. $\times 10^3$.	(AB) at M.R.	$\frac{(AB)^3}{M.R.}$.
$\mu = 0.12$.								
10	5	9.5	2.8	4.80	15.5	26.60	0.853	27.35
5	10	4.8	5.6	9.10	16.5	26.40	0.869	28.61
5	5	4.8	2.8	2.13	17.7	21.70	0.768	27.18
5	7.5	4.8	4.2	5.06	16.7	13.06	0.577	25.49
$\mu = 0.25$.								
10	10	9.6	5.0	20.00	12.00	39.07	0.953	23.25
10	5	9.6	2.5	5.60	10.70	18.80	0.643	21.97
5	10	4.8	5.1	7.60	16.40	17.73	0.623	21.97
5	5	4.8	2.5	1.87	16.13	6.27	0.367	21.45
$\mu = 0.45$.								
10	10	9.6	4.7	9.60	22.08	26.27	0.800	24.37
10	5	9.6	2.2	2.13	21.81	19.93	0.431	16.99
5	10	4.8	4.5	3.86	25.18	9.73	0.504	26.10
5	5	4.8	2.2	0.93	24.98	3.20	0.285	25.38

I.R. = $-d(AB)/dt$ (Initial).

M.R. = $-d(AB)/dt$ (Maximum).

DISCUSSION

The nature of the $\log I$ -time curve of the coloured intermediate $FeS_2O_3^+$ clearly indicates that the rate of decay is not the maximum in the beginning but attains a maximum value after a period of time. With progress of the reaction, the ferrous and the tetrathionate ions replace respectively the ferric and the thiosulphate ions, and as a result there is a decrease in the ionic strength. That the gradual increase in the rate is not due to the change in ionic strength accompanying the reaction is demonstrated by the following considerations.

For a mixture containing initially equal volumes of solutions of strength 0.005M with respect to Fe^{3+} and $S_2O_3^{2-}$ ions, the change in ionic strength at the completion of the reaction would be 0.0175. Working with such a mixture at an ionic strength as high as 0.45, the autocatalytic nature of the curve could be observed and that, when the reaction is far from being complete. This shows that the change in ionic strength cannot be the reason for the increase in the rate of decay. Secondly, the instability constant

$$K_{FeS_2O_3^+} = \frac{[Fe^{3+}][S_2O_3^{2-}]}{[FeS_2O_3^+]}$$

It has been shown by Page (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, 50, 120) that the value of the instability constant decreases with decrease in ionic strength. So for the same concentrations of Fe^{3+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ ions, the concentration of FeS_2O_8^+ becomes more if the ionic strength be less. Let two successive stages of the reaction be imagined in which the concentrations of Fe^{3+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ are almost the same. That stage in which the ionic strength is less would have greater concentration of FeS_2O_8^+ . It is evident therefore that with the progress of the reaction, which is accompanied by a decrease in ionic strength, the concentration of FeS_2O_8^+ at any moment should be more than that at the preceding instant, taking only the effect of the decrease in ionic strength into consideration. In other words, the change in ionic strength goes counter to the increase in the rate of decay observed in this reaction. Since FeS_2O_8^+ is an intermediate and its concentration is maximum when the concentrations of Fe^{3+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ are the maximum at the beginning, it is to be expected that the rate of consumption of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ or that of reduction of Fe^{3+} would be of the same nature as the rate of decay of FeS_2O_8^+ . Experiments carried out (unpublished) confirm that the rate of consumption of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ is not the maximum at the beginning but attains maximum value after a period of time. All the above considerations lead us to accept that the decay of FeS_2O_8^+ must involve an intermediate for explaining the autocatalytic nature of the curve. This intermediate has been suggested by us to possess the formula $\text{Fe}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_2^-$.

Without the assumption of the second intermediate, $\text{Fe}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_2^-$, the manner in which the reaction can be imagined to occur is

If this is so, it is evident that the rate in the beginning must be maximum, since the concentration of FeS_2O_8^+ is the maximum then. Further, as two ion-pairs of the same charge are involved, the rate of decay should increase with the increase in ionic strength, which is contrary to the observed data recorded in Table III. Moreover, the rate at the initial stage should vary as the square of the concentration of FeS_2O_8^+ . In other words, $(\text{Fe}^{3+})^2 (\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-})^2 / \text{initial rate}$ should be constant. This is not so. On the other hand, $(\text{Fe}^{3+}) (\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-})^2 / \text{initial rate}$ is a constant, thereby showing that the initial rate does not vary with the square of FeS_2O_8^+ concentration.

From Table III both the initial and the maximum rates appear to decrease with the increase in ionic strength, suggesting that the rate-determining steps involve ions of opposite signs.

From the mechanism suggested, expressions for the initial and the maximum rates of decay have been derived. The data recorded in Table III are in good agreement with the expressions. The step represented by equation (ii) needs some explanation. In the presence of preponderating concentration of Fe^{3+} , it is worth while questioning the validity of this step. The inclusion of this step has been conceived on the tendency of the ferric ion to form the polynuclear compound $\text{Fe}_n(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_n$, however transient be its existence.

Here, though the mechanism of the ferric thiosulphate reaction has been discussed, the kinetic expression for the rates of decay of the coloured intermediate FeS_2O_3^+ has been derived and corroborated by experimental data. The expression for the rate of consumption of the thiosulphate or that of the reduction of the ferric ion will be published in due course. The mechanism proposed by us differs from the one proposed by Holluta and Martini (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, **141**, 23 ; 1925, **144**, 321) in that our mechanism includes two intermediates, FeS_2O_3^+ and $\text{Fe}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2^-$. Further, all stages of mechanism are simple bimolecular reactions, and it is thus in keeping with the general principle of economy of structural change in each elementary process.

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Received April 2, 1957.